

OSPARK Research Protocol Appendix 1: Data Management Plan

1. Administrative Data

Version of DMP	1.0
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Organisations responsible for DMP	OLS (Open Life Science Ltd), United Kingdom
Collaborating organisations	Digital Research Academy (DRA Digital Research Academy GmbH), Germany
Project title	Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK) Bootcamp
Project acronym	OSPARK
Start date of project	1 January 2025
End date of project	1 January 2027
Grant information	The OSPARK (Open Science Promotion and Advocacy Research Knowledge) Bootcamp project is funded through the OSCARS (Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society) first call. It is part of a broader effort to strengthen open science policy, infrastructure, and training across Europe and globally. OSCARS is funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101129751. The grant was co-awarded to OLS and Digital Research Academy (DRA Digital Research Academy GmbH).
Relevant policies	<p>OLS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Code of Conduct Additional relevant policies regarding research and data are being developed and will apply retroactively when practical. These will be listed on OLS's Policies, Procedures, and Documents page. <p>DRA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Code of Conduct Terms and Conditions

	<p>European Commission</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Funding rules, as indicated via OSCARS
<p>Data summary</p>	<p>The purpose of this data collection is to understand the current knowledge, practices and needs of individuals working in open science. This will inform the design and delivery of the OSPARK Bootcamp, to ensure it is based on actual capacity gaps across open science communities and among open science advocates.</p> <p>The data collection is relevant to the following project outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding the outreach, marketing, and communications roles and responsibilities that open science advocates take on. Identifying systemic or personal barriers that prevent effective outreach and public engagement. Mapping the specific skills and training gaps that participants report needing to better perform advocacy roles. Measuring self-assessed knowledge and confidence levels before and after the Bootcamp to evaluate learning impact. Informing the structure, content, and delivery approach of the OSPARK Bootcamp to directly address the needs uncovered. <p>The data utility is both formative and evaluative. In the early stages of this project, the data will inform the design of the training materials and content delivery. After implementation, it will serve as an impact evaluation tool, contributing to the evidence base around capacity-building for open science outreach.</p>

This Data Management Plan has been written using the following template:

Heider, V., Raffetseder, L., Sanchez Solis, B., & Ulrich, X. (2018). DMP Template for the Social Sciences (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1291816>

2. Data Characteristics

Personnel costs are covered by OLS organisational overheads and the OSPARK OSCARS grant respectively. Data provenance, sourcing, and versioning will be managed by the platforms as the chosen software is all cloud-based.

The intended use of all data is outlined in the associated research protocol. However, it should be noted that this project uses open data sharing practices. Specifically, anonymised datasets will be shared on open GitHub and/or Zenodo repositories under a CC-BY 4.0 license. Reuse of the data beyond the project and by third parties is therefore possible.

2.1. Study 1 (Discussion Groups)

Study 1 will involve the collection of primary data through discussion groups embedded into training workshops. The data will comprise (a) personally identifiable information (names and emails); (b) recordings of workshops; (c) transcripts of workshops; and (d) notes, documents, or other artifacts from discussion groups within the workshops.

Personal details and informed consent will be managed through the event registration platform, either Eventbrite (<https://www.eventbrite.com/>) or the Digital Research Academy's Indico portal (<https://events.digital-research.academy/>). As the discussion groups are integral to both the workshop and research design, taking part in the research will be a requirement for attending the workshop. When participants consent to being contacted about future research or training opportunities, their details will be exported to OLS's customer relationship management software, CiviCRM (<https://civicrm.org/>). This transfer will be done manually by a member of the research team. Personal details will only be reused for activities they have consented to - in this case, to add the individual to a mailing list focused on OLS research and training opportunities.

Recordings of workshops will be made via Zoom (<https://www.zoom.com/>) or a local app (such as Audacity) on the work PC on a research team member. Recordings will be stored on Zoom Cloud and/or the work PCs of OLS employees. Upon completion of a recording, it will be exported to OLS's closed enterprise Google Drive (https://workspace.google.com/intl/en_uk/) and deleted from both Zoom Cloud and the research team member's work PC. This data is expected to be no more than 100GB. Recordings will be deleted from Google Drive after the transcripts have been cross-validated against them.

Automated transcription will be completed using the Otter (<https://otter.ai/>) plugin for Zoom

or DaVinci Resolve. The automated transcripts will be exported from Otter into OLS's closed enterprise Google Drive, only accessible to research team members. The automated transcript will be deleted from Otter after it is exported. During anonymisation, the transcript versioning will be managed in Google Docs. The final anonymised transcripts will be shared publicly through GitHub (<https://github.com/>) and/or Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) under a CC-BY license. These are free services, so no additional costs will be incurred. The final dataset will comprise plain .txt and/or .csv files to ensure maximum compatibility, avoiding proprietary formats. No explicit versioning will be required as the data will not be further transformed beyond anonymisation. Accompanying documents within the repository will include a README file (.md) describing the variables and methods of data analysis.

Study 2 (Survey)

Study 2 will involve the collection of primary data through an online survey designed and developed by the OSPARK research team, based on a pilot by a work group at the Open Science Retreat 2025 in Switzerland. The data will be collected through an anonymous Google Form hosted within OLS's closed enterprise Google Drive. Only members of the research team will have access to the form and its responses during data collection. Responses will be automatically stored in a linked Google Sheets document, from which they will be exported for analysis. Data will be anonymised if needed using Google Sheets, with versioning managed through the included changes tracking.

The amount of data is expected to be no more than 1GB total. All data will be exported in .csv formats, while open-text responses will additionally be exported as .txt files for ease of handling. The final dataset of anonymised survey data and accompanying documents, such as a README file (.md) describing the variables and methods of data analysis, will be archived on Zenodo under a CC-BY 4.0 license, with all files documented and linked to a DOI. Data analysis will be performed in R or Python using the work PCs of members of the research team and GitHub will be used to version-control analysis scripts. No specialised hardware is required.

At the end of the survey, participants will be signposted to a CiviCRM mailing list where they can opt-in to receiving more information about research and training opportunities at OLS, and a Kit mailing list (managed by the Digital Research Agency) where they can receive newsletters about the OSPARK project. Neither will be traceable to their research responses.

Study 3 (Training Evaluation)

Study 3 involves an evaluation of the OSPARK Bootcamp training programme using a

pre-post design. Data will originate from two mixed methods questionnaires, one administered before the training and one after it has concluded. All attendees will be invited to participate in the research, but involvement in the research will not be a requirement to sign up for the training. The data will therefore comprise (a) responses to the consent form, (b) pre-test questionnaire responses, and (c) post-test questionnaire responses.

Consent form responses will be collected through the event hosting platform, either Eventbrite or the Digital Research Academy's Indico portal. Participants will be linked to an information sheet about the study and asked whether they consent to taking part under the terms outlined on the sheet. They will be reminded that this is not a requirement for attending the training programme. Consent information will be managed by the Digital Research Academy and will not be reused.

Participants who do consent will receive two questionnaires—one before the training programme starts and one after it has concluded. These will be hosted on a Google Form within OLS's closed enterprise Google Drive. At the end of the data collection period specified in the project's research protocol, responses to both Google Forms will be combined into one Google Sheet. Participants will be asked to generate a pseudonymous code to allow the research team to link responses between the two questionnaires. Any potentially identifiable information will then be removed, as will the pseudonymous codes. Versioning will be managed through Google Sheets' inbuilt version control system.

The final dataset will comprise the anonymous questionnaire responses and is expected to be under 10GB. This will be shared as a .csv file, and open-text responses will additionally be shared as a .txt file. Materials, anonymised data, and analysis code will be openly shared in a version-controlled GitHub and/or Zenodo repository under a CC-BY 4.0 license. Quantitative analysis will be conducted using R or Python, as specified in the protocol. Given the expected repository size, no additional compute costs are expected to be incurred.

At the end of the course, participants will be signposted to a CiviCRM mailing list where they can opt-in to receiving more information about research and training opportunities at OLS, and a Kit mailing list (managed by the Digital Research Agency) where they can receive newsletters about the OSPARK project. Neither will be traceable to their questionnaire responses.

3. Documentation and Metadata

3.1. Metadata standards

Metadata standards will be identified once the data are collected. Due to the relatively simple nature of the data, there may not be relevant metadata standards to adhere to. Regardless, any metadata practices will be outlined in each dataset's respective README file.

3.2. Documentation

The research protocol and its associated appendices will outline the project's methodology and measures. Materials, datasets, and analysis code will be documented using README files in associated repositories. The README files will contextualise file structures, link to methods, and provide any naming conventions. The repositories will be open and shared with a CC-BY 4.0 license.

3.3. Data quality control

The quality of survey and questionnaire responses will be checked using attention checks built into the questionnaire. Any individual who fails ≥ 2 attention checks will be excluded from analysis.

The quality of qualitative data in study 1 will be checked during the anonymisation process. The automatically generated transcripts will be reviewed by at least two human coders during this. Furthermore, qualitative data analysis will be conducted by one researcher to ensure consistency and reviewed by at least one other researcher.

4. Data Availability and Storage

4.1. Data release and sharing strategy

Anonymised data will be released after anonymisation. All datasets will be archived in an open GitHub and/or Zenodo repository under a CC-BY 4.0 license. A DOI will be assigned. Where applicable, repository metadata will be used to facilitate findability.

4.2. Data storage strategy

All accounts, hardware, and networks used in the study will be compliant with OLS's internal cybersecurity policy.

Information stored on web- or cloud-based platforms will be only accessible by members of the research team. Where individual work accounts are used, permission restrictions will be applied. Where shared team accounts are used, the details will only be shared via encrypted transfer. All accounts will use long, randomly generated strings for passwords and multi-factor authentication will be enabled on all platforms which support it.

Where work PCs are used, they will be kept regularly updated and utilise firewall and antivirus software.

4.3. Data preservation strategy

The majority of data being preserved are the anonymous datasets archived in open repositories on Zenodo and/or GitHub. As these are large, well-funded platforms, the datasets are expected to be retained for at least 10 years, but likely longer.

The raw data and personal information obtained as part of the study will not be preserved, as it does not have utility beyond the study. This data will be deleted at the end of the OSPARK research project or when it is no longer required in the research process (whichever is sooner). The only exception to this deletion rule is where a participant opts to additionally share their details for an OLS or OSPARK mailing list. In this case, the data is internal communications data rather than research data, so will be retained in line with organisational policies.

5. Legal and Ethical Aspects

5.1. Legal Aspects

All platforms used for this project are compliant with United Kingdom General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) legislation. Materials, data analysis code, and anonymised data will be published in Zenodo and/or GitHub repositories under a CC-BY 4.0 license. As such, no significant legal or copyright concerns are anticipated.

The risk of a data breach is expected to be minimal due to the data storage strategy (see §4.2). In case of a data breach, a post-incident investigation will occur, and if appropriate, OLS will report the incident to the UK's [Information Commissioner's Office](#).

5.2. Ethical Aspects

The research project will be conducted in compliance with the British Psychological Society Code of Human Research Ethics (2021).¹ Across all studies, potential participants will be provided an information sheet which outlines the purpose of the research, what the study involves, potential risks or benefits of participation, what will happen to their data, and the open science practices being used. This research project will be reviewed by Pearl IRB, a US-based ethics review board for researchers and organisations not associated with a university.

Participants in the OSPARK Bootcamp will be open science advocates. These will be overwhelmingly individuals who have studied and conducted research at least to the level of a Masters degree. They are also expected to have good knowledge of open science practices. Assessing the potential benefits and risks of taking part in this research will therefore fall within their professional competencies. Regardless, the participant information sheet provided as part of the informed consent process will highlight the potential risks unique to participation in the project, such as career or reputation risk from sharing certain information about their open science initiatives, institutions, or collaborators.

¹ Oates, J., Carpenter, D., Fisher, M., Goodson, S., Hannah, B., Kwiatowski, R., ... & Wainwright, T. (2021, April). *BPS Code of Human Research Ethics*. British Psychological Society.
<https://doi.org/10.53841/bpsrep.2021.inf180>

